

Electrochemical behaviour of 1-benzenesulfonyl-3-benzenesulfanamido-4-(4'-substituted-arylhydrazono)-2-pyrazolin-5-ones

D. N. Satyanarayana^a, L. K. Ravindranath^a, T. Ravi Sankar^b and P. Venkata Ramana^{b*}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Sri Krishnadevaraya University, Anantapur-515 003, India

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Sri Krishnadevaraya University Post-Graduate Centre, Kurnool-518 002, India

E-mail : ramanapeddakotla@yahoo.co.in Fax : 91-8518-276183

Manuscript received 4 October 2002, revised 10 December 2003, accepted 10 March 2004

The electrochemical behaviour of 1-benzenesulfonyl-3-benzenesulfanamido-4-(4'-substituted-arylhydrazono)-2-pyrazolin-5-ones has been investigated at dme and gc electrodes in buffer solutions of pH 1.1–10.2 using dc polarography, cyclic voltammetry and coulometry. The compounds exhibit one well defined wave in acidic solutions and two waves in alkaline solutions. The process is irreversible and diffusion-controlled. Preparative controlled potential electrolysis indicates that aromatic amine and 1-benzenesulfonyl-3-benzenesulfanamido-4-amino-2-pyrazolin-5-one are products of electrolysis. The mechanism of the reduction and the effect of solvent composition have been studied.

Many pyrazoline derivatives are well known for their biological activity¹. The redox characteristics of such biological substances may provide valuable information about the redox behavior in living systems². In view of the biological activity of pyrazolines and the usefulness of electrochemical techniques in studying biological molecules, some 1-benzenesulfonyl-3-benzenesulfanamido-4-(4'-substituted-arylhydrazono)-2-pyrazolin-5-ones have been studied at dropping mercury and glassy carbon electrodes.

Results and discussion

Wave in acidic pH's :

1-Benzenesulfonyl-3-benzenesulfanamido-2-pyrazolin-5-one failed to exhibit a polarographic wave. This is attributed to the stabilization of the pyrazoline ring by keto-enol tautomerism. The waves (Fig. 1) that are observed in compounds **1-6** given in the Scheme 1 are therefore attributed to the polarographic reduction of exocyclic azomethine group ($>NH-N=C<$). These compounds exhibit a single wave in acidic solutions. The electrochemical characteristics of the compounds are presented in Tables 1 and 2. The low value of temperature coefficient (below $1.62\% K^{-1}$) and the direct proportionality observed for i_d vs concentration and i_d vs $h^{1/2}$, indicate the diffusion-controlled nature of the electrode process. The shift in $E_{1/2}$ towards more negative potential with increase in concentration of depolariser and semi-log plots³ confirmed the irreversible nature of the wave. $E_{1/2}$ values were also found to become more negative with increase in pH before reaching a limit-

Fig. 1. Polarograms of 1-benzenesulfonyl-3-benzenesulfanamido-4-(arylhydrazono)-2-pyrazolin-5-one. Concn. = 1 mM; medium = 40% (v/v) aqueous DMF.

ing value beyond a pH of 8.2. This clearly shows the participation of protons in the reduction process. The value of αn_a (product of transfer coefficient $[\alpha]$ and number of electrons transferred in the rate determining step) and P (the number of protons involved in the rate determining step) are determined using following expression³.

$$E_{1/2} - E_{1/4} = \frac{0.0517}{\alpha n_a} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\Delta E_{1/2}}{\Delta pH} = \frac{0.05915}{\alpha n_a} P \quad (2)$$

The value of diffusion coefficient has been determined by Ilkovic⁴ equation,

$$i_d = 607 n D^{1/2} m^{2/3} t^{1/6} C \quad (3)$$

where n = number of electrons transferred in the process, m = rate of mercury flow in mg/s, D = diffusion constant of depolariser in cm²/s, t = drop time in s, C = depolariser concentration in millimoles/litre, i_d = diffusion current in micro amperes.

The value of heterogeneous rate constant ($k_{f,h}^o$) has been evaluated by Meites and Israel⁵ equation,

$$-E_{1/2} = -0.2412 + \frac{0.05915}{\alpha n_a} \log \frac{1.349 k_{f,h}^o t^{1/2}}{D^{1/2}} \quad (4)$$

The activation free energy change (ΔG^*) has been determined by the relationship,

$$k_{f,h}^o = \frac{kT}{h} r_o \exp \left(\frac{-\Delta G^*}{RT} \right) \quad (5)$$

where k is the Boltzman constant, h the Plank's constant, r_o the mean distance between the depolarised ions in the bulk solution, R the gas constant and T the absolute temperature. In general the value of r_o is taken as 2×10^{-8} cm⁶.

Waves in alkaline pH's :

Each compound of the series (1-6) exhibits two waves in the pH range 8.3–10.2. The half-wave potential of the wave in alkaline solutions is not altered with change in hydroxyl ion concentration. The height of the first wave decreases with increase in pH and the wave height vs pH plot assumes the form of dissociation curve (~) in the pH range

Table 1. Polarographic data of compounds 1-6

Concn. = 1 mM, medium = 40% (v/v) DMF

pH	$-E_{1/2}$ V vs SCE												i_{lim} μ A											
	I wave						II wave						I wave						II wave					
	1	2	3	4	5	6	1	2	3	4	5	6	1	2	3	4	5	6	1	2	3	4	5	6
1.1	0.51	0.54	0.57	0.44	0.61	0.41							12.4	12.8	13.0	11.5	11.8	12.5						
2.1	0.63	0.69	0.71	0.57	0.75	0.50							12.4	12.6	12.5	11.5	11.6	12.5						
3.6	0.70	0.74	0.80	0.65	0.82	0.55							12.0	11.8	12.1	11.0	11.2	11.4						
4.6	0.77	0.81	0.87	0.71	0.87	0.65							11.4	11.0	11.5	10.4	10.5	10.7						
5.6	0.87	0.91	0.94	0.80	0.97	0.74							10.8	10.0	10.4	9.7	9.8	9.8						
8.3	1.24	1.30	1.35	1.15	1.37	1.10	1.57	1.64	1.67	1.50	1.71	1.40	6.5	7.0	7.5	6.5	6.4	7.2	8.6	9.2	9.0	9.2	9.0	7.8
9.2	1.24	1.30	1.35	1.15	1.37	1.10	1.57	1.64	1.67	1.50	1.71	1.40	6.2	6.5	6.4	5.3	5.6	5.8	9.0	9.6	9.7	9.8	9.5	8.2
10.2	1.24	1.30	1.35	1.15	1.37	1.10	1.57	1.64	1.67	1.50	1.71	1.40	6.0	5.9	6.1	4.8	5.0	5.2	10.2	10.4	10.4	10.4	10.2	9.6

Table 2. Polarographic characteristics and kinetic parameters of compounds 1- 6 at pH 4.6 and 8.3

pH	Compd.	$\Delta E_{1/2}/\Delta pH$		ωn_a		Number of protons		$D \times 10^6$ cm ² /s		$k_{f,h}^o$ cm/s		ΔG^* kcal mol ⁻¹	
		I wave	II wave	I wave	II wave	I wave	II wave	I wave	II wave	I wave	II wave		
		4.6	1	0.12	0.57	-	1.15	-	6.80	-	8.94×10^{-9}	-	18.36
	2	0.12	0.43	-	0.87	-	6.33	-	7.88×10^{-8}	-	17.04	-	
	3	0.12	0.43	-	0.87	-	6.92	-	3.02×10^{-8}	-	17.62	-	
	4	0.083	0.57	-	0.80	-	5.66	-	3.09×10^{-8}	-	17.61	-	
	5	0.12	0.57	-	1.16	-	5.77	-	8.95×10^{-10}	-	19.75	-	
	6	0.12	0.65	-	1.32	-	5.99	-	3.37×10^{-8}	-	17.55	-	
8.3	1	0.12	0.74	0.64	1.50	-	2.21	15.49	2.03×10^{-16}	7.05×10^{-18}	29.03	31.07	
	2	0.12	0.64	0.74	1.30	-	2.56	17.72	2.39×10^{-15}	5.69×10^{-21}	27.53	35.38	
	3	0.12	0.65	0.65	1.32	-	2.94	16.96	4.79×10^{-16}	3.50×10^{-19}	28.51	32.89	
	4	0.083	0.86	0.74	1.21	-	2.21	17.72	3.89×10^{-17}	3.21×10^{-19}	30.03	32.94	
	5	0.12	0.65	0.74	1.32	-	2.14	8.58	2.46×10^{-16}	5.72×10^{-22}	28.31	36.78	
	6	0.12	0.87	0.86	1.76	-	2.71	12.74	1.64×10^{-16}	2.16×10^{-20}	29.16	34.58	

R = 1, H; 2, CH₃; 3, OCH₃; 4, Cl; 5, OH; 6, COOC₂H₅

Scheme 1

of study (1.1–10.2) while the height of the second wave increases with increase in hydroxyl ion concentration. Literature survey reveals that azo group exhibits azo-hydrazone tautomerism in benzeneazo-pyrazolin-5-ones⁷. In alkaline solution arylhydrazono-pyrazolin-5-one (I) exists in the azomethine anionic form⁸ (II, cf. Scheme 1). The decrease in the limiting current with increase in pH may be attributed to the presence of acid-base equilibrium.

Cyclic voltammetry :

The compounds (1-6) gave two cathodic peaks at high scan rates (100–500 mV/s) and one cathodic peak at low scan rates (10–50 mV/s) at glassy carbon (gc) electrode in the pH range 1.1–5.6. No anodic peak is observed in the reverse scan in any media indicating irreversible nature of the electrode process (Fig. 2). This is further supported by the negative shift in the peak potential with the increasing sweep rate (Tables 3 and 4). The plots of i_{pc} vs concentration and i_{pc} vs $v^{1/2}$ fulfil the criteria of the diffusion controlled nature^{9,10} of the electrode process. The plots of E_{pc} vs pH are similar to $E_{1/2}$ vs pH plots and this lends support to the findings of the dc polarography. But in contrast to a single reduction wave observed in dc polarography in acidic solution (pH 1.1–5.6), two cathodic peaks are observed at high scan rates (100–500 mV/s) in cyclic voltammetric studies. The two cathodic peaks observed in acidic pH's at high scan rates therefore suggest that the reduction is taking place in two steps. The peak potential data show that the potentials are very close to each other. Further that these two peaks are observed in cyclic voltammetric studies only at high scan rates indicates that these steps are quite fast. The

steps are so fast that they can not be resolved into two waves at low polarographic scan rates. Therefore they merge with each other and manifest as a single wave. This is probably the reason for the presence of a single wave instead of two waves in d.c. polarography.

Fig. 2. Cyclic voltammograms of 1-benzenesulfonyl-3-benzene-sulfanamido-4-(arylhydrazono)-2-pyrazolin-5-one. Concn. = 1 mM; medium = 40% (v/v) aqueous DMF : (a) pH 4.6 and (b) pH 8.3; scan rate = 0.10 V s⁻¹.

Table 3. Cyclic voltammetric data of compounds 1-6 at pH 4.6

Concn. = 1 mM, medium = 40% (v/v) DMF

pH	Compd.	Scan rate	$-E_{pc1}$	$-E_{pcII}$	$-E_{pcinv}$	i_{pc1}	i_{pcII}	i_{pcinv}
		$V s^{-1}$	V	V	V	μA	μA	μA
4.6	1	0.010	0.89	-	0.67	0.75	-	3.14
		0.020	0.91	-	0.67	1.02	-	2.34
		0.050	0.93	-	0.67	1.67	-	1.89
		0.100	0.95	1.10	0.70	2.40	2.00	1.40
		0.200	0.98	1.12	0.73	3.42	2.85	1.10
		0.300	1.00	1.15	0.75	4.20	3.41	0.80
		0.500	1.04	1.19	0.80	5.40	4.25	0.67
	2	0.010	0.96	-	0.62	0.62	-	2.59
		0.020	0.98	-	0.62	0.90	-	1.94
		0.050	1.00	-	0.62	1.44	-	1.74
		0.100	1.02	1.12	0.65	2.10	1.95	1.20
		0.200	1.04	1.14	0.68	3.04	2.80	0.74
		0.300	1.07	1.16	0.70	3.56	3.46	0.65
		0.500	1.10	1.20	0.73	4.60	4.45	0.47
	3	0.010	1.30	-	0.69	0.75	-	3.10
		0.020	1.31	-	0.69	1.26	-	2.30
		0.050	1.33	-	0.69	1.78	-	1.85
		0.100	1.35	1.44	0.72	2.60	2.10	1.30
		0.200	1.37	1.47	0.75	3.75	3.12	0.84
		0.300	1.39	1.50	0.77	4.95	3.92	0.47
		0.500	1.43	1.53	0.81	6.45	4.97	0.31
4	0.010	0.78	-	0.64	0.70	-	2.38	
	0.020	0.80	-	0.64	0.98	-	1.74	
	0.050	0.82	-	0.64	1.54	-	1.48	
	0.100	0.84	0.95	0.67	2.30	1.90	1.00	
	0.200	0.87	0.97	0.70	3.37	2.94	0.64	
	0.300	0.90	0.99	0.73	4.35	3.72	0.39	
	0.500	0.94	1.04	0.75	5.68	4.53	0.24	
5	0.010	1.33	-	0.64	0.80	-	3.92	
	0.020	1.35	-	0.64	1.16	-	3.03	
	0.050	1.37	-	0.64	1.57	-	2.57	
	0.100	1.40	1.52	0.67	2.45	2.00	1.80	
	0.200	1.43	1.55	0.70	3.58	3.20	1.16	
	0.300	1.47	1.58	0.73	4.47	3.86	0.80	
	0.500	1.50	1.62	0.77	5.86	4.95	0.56	
6	0.010	0.67	-	0.61	0.65	-	2.30	
	0.020	0.69	-	0.61	0.87	-	1.80	
	0.050	0.71	-	0.61	1.32	-	1.50	
	0.100	0.73	0.84	0.64	2.10	1.70	1.00	
	0.200	0.76	0.87	0.66	3.15	2.64	0.90	
	0.300	0.78	0.90	0.68	3.94	3.26	0.75	
	0.500	0.82	0.94	0.71	5.20	4.38	0.65	

Table 4. Cyclic voltammetric data of compounds 1-6 at pH 8.3

Concn. = 1 mM, medium = 40% (v/v) DMF

pH	Compd.	Scan rate	$-E_{pc1}$	$-E_{pcII}$	i_{pc1}	i_{pcII}
		$V s^{-1}$	V	V	μA	μA
8.3	1	0.010	1.30	1.36	0.48	0.36
		0.020	1.32	1.38	0.70	0.50
		0.050	1.34	1.40	1.08	0.82
		0.100	1.36	1.42	1.60	1.20
		0.200	1.39	1.43	2.20	1.75
		0.300	1.41	1.46	2.68	2.14
		0.500	1.45	1.50	3.49	2.76
	2	0.010	1.35	1.45	0.36	0.27
		0.020	1.37	1.46	0.55	0.40
		0.050	1.40	1.48	0.87	0.62
		0.100	1.42	1.50	1.20	0.90
		0.200	1.45	1.53	1.74	1.34
		0.300	1.47	1.55	2.16	1.65
		0.500	1.51	1.59	2.75	2.10
	3	0.010	1.39	1.52	0.35	0.24
		0.020	1.41	1.54	0.56	0.30
		0.050	1.43	1.56	0.87	0.67
		0.100	1.45	1.58	1.00	0.80
		0.200	1.48	1.61	2.00	1.35
		0.300	1.51	1.63	2.04	1.67
		0.500	1.55	1.67	3.00	2.15
4	0.010	1.19	1.31	0.36	0.25	
	0.020	1.20	1.33	0.45	0.30	
	0.050	1.23	1.35	0.68	0.47	
	0.100	1.25	1.38	1.10	0.86	
	0.200	1.28	1.41	1.76	1.25	
	0.300	1.31	1.43	2.20	1.68	
	0.500	1.34	1.47	2.91	2.20	
5	0.010	1.44	1.55	0.32	0.24	
	0.020	1.45	1.57	0.42	0.35	
	0.050	1.47	1.59	0.90	0.69	
	0.100	1.50	1.62	1.00	0.82	
	0.200	1.53	1.65	1.75	1.40	
	0.300	1.56	1.67	2.10	1.72	
	0.500	1.60	1.71	3.08	2.20	
6	0.010	1.08	1.19	0.28	0.23	
	0.020	1.10	1.20	0.40	0.30	
	0.050	1.12	1.22	0.65	0.47	
	0.100	1.14	1.25	0.95	0.78	
	0.200	1.17	1.27	1.42	1.30	
	0.300	1.20	1.30	1.96	1.63	
	0.500	1.22	1.34	2.48	2.21	

A cathodic peak during anodic cycle is observed in the pH range 1.1–5.6. Such peaks known as inverted peaks are reported in literature¹⁰ and these probably arise either due to movement of mercury electrode surface as a result of uneven drop polarization (similar to polarographic maximum) or due to inhibition of electrode reaction as a result of consequence of coverage of the electrode surface by a product of the electrode reaction¹¹. The first possibility is ruled out since cyclic voltammetric studies are carried out with gc electrode.

Controlled potential electrolysis :

Progress of electrolysis was followed by recording the decreasing current with time and the number of electrons per molecule were computed from *i-t* curves following the procedure outlined by Lingane¹² and found to be about four (3.6–3.8). The electrolysis is carried out until the electrolysed solution did not exhibit any polarographic wave or a cyclic voltammetric peak.

Effect of solvent composition :

Effect of solvent compositions on the polarographic characteristics of compounds 1-6 was studied by recording polarograms in 50 and 75% organic solvent solutions (dimethylformamide, dimethylsulfoxide, aceto nitrile and methyl alcohol)-water solutions at pH 4.6 (Table 5). It was observed that half-wave potential shifted to more negative values¹³ in the presence of organic co-solvent and the magnitude of the shift depends on the nature of the solvent. The order of the shift observed in the present study is $\text{CH}_3\text{OH} > \text{CH}_3\text{CN} > \text{DMF} > \text{DMSO}$. The shift of half-wave potential towards more negative values and decrease in the limiting current values with increase in the percentage of organic co-solvents, may be due to rise in pH of the solution¹³ which results in the increase in the dissociation constant of the

Fig. 3. Plot of $-E_{1/2}$ (V) vs σ_p .

protonated species¹⁴. Both these factors lower the rate of protonation and consequently lead to a shift in $E_{1/2}$ of the reduction wave (in case where protonation precedes the electron transfer) towards more negative potential.

Effects of substituents on reduction :

To establish the effect of substituents on the polarographic reduction, $E_{1/2}$ was plotted against the Hammett substituent constant (Fig. 3). The substituent constant σ used were taken from the literature¹⁵. It is observed from the plot that the electron donating substituent, $-\text{CH}_3$, $-\text{OCH}_3$ and $-\text{OH}$ shifts $E_{1/2}$ towards more negative values while electrons withdrawing groups $-\text{Cl}$ and $-\text{COOC}_2\text{H}_5$ shifts $E_{1/2}$ towards more positive values. The correlation coefficient calculated for the $E_{1/2}$ vs σ plot ($r = 1.0$) show satisfactory application of Hammett's correlation to the system under study. The positive value of the specific reaction constant ($\rho = 0.27$ at pH 4.6) suggests that the electron addition step is more important than the addition of proton. The results also suggest that the presence of substituents do not affect the mechanism of reduction but only makes the reduction either easier or more difficult depending on the nature of the substituent.

Table 5. Effect of organic co-solvent on $E_{1/2}$ of compounds 1-6

Concn. = 1 mM, pH = 4.6

Compd.	$-E_{1/2}$ V vs SCE				$-E_{1/2}$ V vs SCE			
	DMSO	DMF	CH_3CN	CH_3OH	DMSO	DMF	CH_3CN	CH_3OH
	50%	50%	50%	50%	75%	75%	75%	75%
1	0.76	0.83	0.86	0.90	0.84	0.91	0.95	1.03
2	0.82	0.88	0.91	0.95	0.91	0.97	0.99	1.08
3	0.89	0.94	0.96	1.02	0.97	1.04	1.08	1.14
4	0.69	0.76	0.80	0.85	0.77	0.87	0.92	1.00
5	0.89	0.96	0.98	1.02	0.98	1.07	1.13	1.20
6	0.65	0.72	0.75	0.80	0.74	0.81	0.90	0.99

Experimental

Compounds **1-6** were synthesized by the literature method¹⁶ and purified by recrystallisation. The structure of these compounds were confirmed by elemental and spectral analyses. Stock solutions ($1 \times 10^{-3} M$) of all the compounds were prepared in dimethylformamide (A.R.). Buffer solutions of pH 1.1 and 2.1 (HCl, KCl), 3.6–5.6 (sodium acetate, acetic acid) and 8.3–10.2 (ammonium chloride, ammonia) and potassium chloride (1.0 M KCl) solutions were prepared in double-distilled water using A.R. grade chemicals. The equipment used and the experimental details are reported elsewhere¹⁷.

The controlled potential electrolysis was carried out in a Lingane H-type cell. A large pool of mercury at the bottom of the smaller compartment served as the anode. The cathode compartment contained 10 ml of 0.01 M 1-benzenesulfonyl-3-benzenesulfanamido-4-(arylhydrazono)-2-pyrazolin-5-one, 30 ml of DMF, 10 ml of 1.0 M KCl and 50 ml of buffer (pH 4.6). Controlled potential electrolysis was carried out at a potential of $-1.1 V$ which is slightly higher than the reduction peak.

After disconnecting the electrolysis cell 1 ml of the resulting solution was withdrawn and presence of aromatic amine in this solution was revealed by the standard spot test¹⁸. The remaining reaction mixture was partially evaporated on a water bath to half of its volume, allowed to cool to RT and extracted with ether. The ether layer was partially evaporated under diminished pressure and the yellow crystalline solid was purified by column chromatography. Elution was done with methanol using silica gel as adsorbent. A number of fractions were collected with the help of automatic fraction collector. These fractions were tested for homogeneity by TLC using benzene : methanol 4 : 1 (v/v). The fractions exhibiting a single spot with R_f value 0.62 (corresponding to heterocyclic amine) were combined and the solvent was evaporated on a water-bath. The yellow crystalline solid thus obtained was identified as 1-benzenesulfonyl-3-benzenesulfanamido-4-amino-2-pyrazolin-5-one by elemental analysis, TLC, IR and ¹H NMR data. The fractions exhibiting a spot with R_f value 0.54 (corresponding to aromatic amine) and other fractions exhibiting more than one spot were discarded (Found : C, 44.20; H 3.36; N 14.60; S, 16.32. Calcd. for : C, 45.68; H 3.55; N, 14.21; S, 16.24%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3450 and 3230 (-NH), 3040 (Ar-H), 1670 (CO cyclic), 1590, 1530 and 1495 (aromatic ring), 1468 and 1460 (five membered heterocyclic ring), 1365, 1155 (-SO₂-) and 1210 cm^{-1} (N-C₆H₅); ¹H

NMR δ (ppm) 3.7 (b, -NH₂), 4.6 (b, -NH), 2.9 (s, -CH), 6.7–7.9 (aromatic proton multiplets).

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (P.V.R.) thanks the U.G.C., New Delhi, for the award of a Minor Research Project.

References

1. H. A. Etman, E. G. Sadek and M. A. Melwally, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1990, **67**, 213; K. Voski and H. Kita, *Ber. Busenges Phys. Chem.*, 1987, **91**, 447.
2. R. Jain and P. Padmaja, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1997, **75**, 567.
3. L. Meites, "Polarographic Techniques", Interscience, New York, 1967; B. Jani and P. J. Elving, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1969, **116**, 1087; R. Jain and Anju Dixit, *J. Croatica Chem. Acta*, 1986, **59**, 463.
4. D. Ilkovic, *Coll. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1934, **6**, 498.
5. L. Meites and Y. Israel, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 4903.
6. P. Delahay, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 4944.
7. G. De Simoni, G. Tacconi, A. Barco and G. P. Pollini, "Natural Products Synthesis Through Pericyclic Reactions", A.C.S., Washington, 1983; A. P. Kozikowski in "Comprehensive Heterocyclic Chemistry", eds. A. R. Katritzky and C. W. Rees, Pergamon, Oxford, 1984, Vol. 1, p. 453; B. R. Lipshutz, *Chem. Rev.*, 1986, **86**, 795.
8. P. Caramella and P. Grunanger in "1,3 Dipolar Cyclo Addition Chemistry", ed. A. Padwa, Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1984, Vol. 1, p. 364.
9. R. S. Nicholson and I. Shain, *Anal. Chem.*, 1964, **36**, 706.
10. R. Fleet and R. D. Jee, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1970, **25**, 397.
11. P. Margaretha and P. Tissot, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1979, **39**, 127; P. Tissot and P. Margaretha, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1978, **23**, 1040.
12. J. J. Lingane, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 1916.
13. A. Cisak, *Rolz. Chim.*, 1962, **36**, 1895.
14. S. G. Mairanovskii, *Talanta*, 1965, **12**, 1299.
15. P. Zuman, "Substituent Effects in Organic Polarography", Plenum Press, New York, 1967, p. 46.
16. H. G. Garg and C. Prakash, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, **9**, 801; M. H. Elnagdi and S. U. Abdallah, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1973, **315**, 1009.
17. P. Venkataramana, D. N. Satyanarayana, L. K. Ravindranath and D. Vasudevan, *J. Electrochem. Soc. India*, 1998, **47**, 1; A. Ramesh, L. K. Ravindranath and S. B. Rao, *Bull. Electrochem.*, 1993, **9**, 112.
18. F. Feigl, "Spot Test", 4th. ed., Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1954, Vol. 2, p. 109.